

Making musicals in the metaverse: building AI-assisted live performances in VR with Imminent-XR

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The next generation of immersive theatre production is being built with AI in the metaverse, creating an online global performance platform. This case study responds to two questions: How will this influx of technology shape the nature of multi-media production in computer-generated environments? And how can performers and producers retain control of their work now that Generative AI can make copyright-free digital replicas of their creative output?

In 2020, the world shut down due to the COVID-19 pandemic, throwing many industries, including theatre, into a tailspin. In-person performances were banned or heavily limited, forcing artists to come up with innovative solutions in order to continue producing art. Just as the COVID-19 restrictions eased, Chat-GPT launched, the crest of a wave of generative artificial intelligence (or Gen AI) tools that have swept through society. These Gen AI tools, combined with existing virtual reality (VR) and gaming technology, are offering new virtual performance spaces that are globally accessible to performers, producers, and audiences.

Imminent-XR, an acronym for IMMersive INteractive ENTertainment in eXtended Reality, was founded from a collaboration catalysed by a Broadway technology incubator during the COVID-19 pandemic. The company is a pioneer in this space, adapting and combining a plethora of different tools with decades of performance production experience, to create virtual theatre for the audience of the future.

With new technologies and approaches come both new and returning challenges: how can we adapt performances to take advantage of emerging screen-based 3D performance platforms made using Virtual and Augmented Reality systems? ? And how does the nature of large language and imaging models, which ingest and learn from copious amounts of data to produce their outputs, impact on the copyright and ownership of that data and outputs by artists? Copyright and governance concerns are a familiar concern in the creative industries, so how are Gen AI tools changing the conversation here?

With the use of Gen AI becoming more prevalent within the Creative Industries, companies have to adapt to the emerging toolsets and the ethical implications that come with using them. Operating at the cutting edge of performance technology, Imminent-XR combines both research and practice

in its work, and hence strives to establish novel ethical work practices around virtual production techniques. This case study explores the ways that Gen AI, Virtual Reality, ethics, and performance are colliding, and how Imminent-XR is approaching both the challenges and opportunities of this confluence.

Convergent Technologies

Digital theatre is a space which is constantly evolving and identifying new uses for emerging and existing tools. For example, by modelling a physical theatre as a digital twin, producers can explore different set design and lighting for a space. Furthermore, digital theatre allows for the breaking of conventions that physical theatre may be limited by. This can go so far as removing physical constraints like gravity, opening up a host of new options for set design and immersive storytelling which can be “quite liberating” - Mary Stewart-David. Imminent-XR uses these lack of constraints to tell immersive and innovative stories within the digital realm.

As a PhD spin-out, founded by theatre and film practitioners, Imminent-XR employs a range of cutting edge creative technologies drawn from video games, immersive theatre, music technology, virtual production techniques for film, and Social VR and 3D networking platforms. Games engines, such as Unity and Epic Games’ Unreal Engine, form the bedrock of the work making computer-generated immersive and interactive environments for virtual musical theatre production.

Imminent-XR uses a range of browser-based commercial VR platforms, such as Virbela’s browser-based VR platform, as a foundation for their digital live performances. This platform can be accessed in realtime from any browser in 2D, as well as in 3D through a VR or MR Headset such as the Meta Quest 3 or the Apple Vision Pro. The platform is great for its versatility; for example, Imminent-XR’s scenographer, Rob Morgan built a complete replica set and theatre in a browser-based VR platform for a virtual production of Sondheim’s *A Little Night Music*, as a digital twin of a physical stage production which he also designed.

Figure 1: A scene featuring Leslie Alexander and performed with the Denver Center for the Performing Arts.

Alt-text: A scene from a physical production of A Little Night Music where a woman in a wheelchair, wearing a white, old-fashioned dress with ruffles and a patterned skirt and under the spotlight is singing on a balcony.

When creating 3D environments or objects for digital performances, Imminent-XR uses a number of different tools such as Blender or SketchUp. These virtual worlds can be replicas of an existing set or can be a new creation. Once the models of these digiworlds are made, they can be imported into a game engine for greater lighting and interactivity control. These environments can then be used in VR to create an immersive experience for an audience using Gen AI in real time to create interactive production assets. *Figures 2 and 3: The same set and characters from A Little Night*

Figure 2:

A Little Night Music in Unreal

Figure 3:

A Little Night Music in FrameVR

Music replicated in a game engine and 3D models for pre-production and 3D visualisation.

Alt-text: The balcony set from A Little Night Music recreated with the characters in a games engine for pre-production and a 3D visualisation of the set. The set is a light coloured balcony with two turrets either side, and a red curtained backdrop. There is a figure standing in the centre of the balcony. Both images have different rendering and details due to the different tools used to create them.

In digital performance, actors are typically represented by avatars, or digital twins. When making digital replicas of human actors, Imminent-XR typically uses third-party software to make customisable avatars which can be rigged for animation with AI driven scripting for multilingual dialogue.

Figure 4: *Demonstration of live facial tracking in a browser-based VR Platform.(credit: Prof Rob Morgan)*

Alt-text: A moving image of two white male performers. Both have brown hair and clear glasses, and wear a blue shirt. They stand in front of a red curtain backdrop and are talking to the camera.

Many of Imminent-XR's virtual production techniques use technologies derived from film and audio

Figure 5: *An AI-generated chatbot character with multilingual voice cloning capability made with a commercially available text-to-video tool.*

Alt-text: An AI animated character picture of an older woman with glasses dressed in an old fashioned cream shirt and beige jacket, holding a newspaper. The character is speaking. This was created using a commercially available AI generation tool

production. Imminent-XR works in both Green screen and LED volume studios to composite real actors into computer-generated environments built in a games engine. . Motion tracking, voice cloning, and facial scanning of actors can also be used to animate avatars in great detail, increasing the audience's immersion for live and recorded performance. When using spatial audio, Imminent-XR uses state-of-the-art recording studios and digital music software to compose and arrange recorded soundtracks with live vocals, lip-synced to the VR character in real time. Virtual reality performance environments afford them spatial audio, which makes sound reproduction especially complex, but allows for a more natural soundscape for the audience, who will experience changes of volume and direction as they move freely about the digital space.

The release and swift growth of Gen AI tools has changed the speed and cost of creating digital content. Imminent-XR is experimenting with these new technologies to see how they can positively impact digital theatre. While not espousing totally non-human automated interactive live performance, this offers the prospect of reaching a wider audience globally across many different time zones, with personalised entertainment operating in many different languages and cultural norms.

Figure 6:
Madame X Composite

Figure 7:
Madame X green screen

Figures 6 and 7: Bringing a painting to life in VR: The Portrait of Madame X - a new musical based on John Singer Sargent's famous painting and its equally infamous subject.

Alt-text: An actress being filmed on a visual production set. The actress is then composited onto the Madame X painting creating an interactive experience.

A new way to play

Traditional musical theatre shows have a long runtime, fixed performance times and a typically passive audience. This doesn't translate well to VR where performances need to be shorter, with more opportunities for audience interaction. Immersive theatre performances, where the audience can explore the virtual setting, talk with actors and interact with the action of the play, help to increase engagement, and give the participants video game-style agency, with the ability to role-play and influence narrative outcomes.

Similarly, audience avatars can be costumed and customised to facilitate active roleplay in the show, while Gen AI tools, such as chatbots based on large language models tailored to the setting, can personalise the experience for the user.

Creative technologies, such as VR and AI can also facilitate pre-production and visualisation for

physical theatre shows, by providing digital twins of stages and sets, allowing production companies to collaborate and rehearse together remotely. This is currently demonstrated by David Gochfeld, an Imminent-XR expert in residence, who is leading a project supported by XR Network+ to build a virtual rehearsal room for the Royal Shakespeare Company.

"We can do everything that we can do in a physical theatre in VR, with the benefit of being able to do it remotely. So when we do shows, our actors are quite often remote in a different country... it doesn't matter to us where people are physically located, we can work together to produce shows and our audience can be anywhere as well." - Mary Stewart-David, Imminent-XR

For Imminent-XR, beyond the creative and collaborative opportunities that the combination of Gen AI and VR offer, the potential for wider access to theatrical performances is also a huge positive.

"The Royal Shakespeare Company did a virtual production inspired by Midsummer Night's Dream, simply called Dream. That performance demonstrated the idea that your audience can, in the thousands, attend a performance from anywhere in the world. It's quite an exciting idea, particularly if we have another pandemic or something like that where we're limited in what we can do as a community of artists and patrons together." - Robert Morgan, Imminent-XR

"One of the more exciting things for me is this concept of accessibility...there's a lot we ask of an audience, but in a virtual space someone that can't get to the theater, a little girl in Kansas who may have just fallen in love with musical theater or a specific musical can potentially log in from where she is and be excited and inspired to see a good quality production" - Robert Morgan, Imminent-XR

Who owns a performance in the age of AI?

There is a long history of copyright infringement in the Creative Industries; now Gen AI has made this process ubiquitous and difficult to police. From set design rip-offs and art forgeries to illicit song sharing, artists have struggled historically to find ways to promote their work without exposing themselves to copyright theft. While Gen AI can be an amazing creative tool for artists, it is also proving to be a major disruptor of their industry.

From Gen AI tools producing replicas of the Mona Lisa in the style of The Simpsons, to actors seeing their faces in political propaganda videos they never filmed, ownership and control of creative works is top of the Gen AI agenda for many in the creative industries. The EU AI Act does mandate a "sufficiently detailed description" of the data used to train models, which may make it easier for creatives to identify if their work has been included in large model training data sets, however no such legislation currently exists in the UK.

For Imminent-XR, approaching ownership and copyright in an ethical way is core to their ways of working, whether experimental or commercial. Embracing the "3 C's": consent, compensation, and control, they aim to work within an ethical framework which gives creatives rights over their work even when augmented by AI.

As Imminent-XR works across international borders, it is also difficult to know which country's copyright regulation and IP governance applies to their creative work, further complicating the picture: *"Robert's in St Louis. The VR Platform is in California, and it's being relayed to us in London via a server centre somewhere in Europe."*

"We're working in human fragments. If you look at the performer, we're taking their voice, their

appearance, a scan of their face, their character in performance in a particular work. These elements can all be employed separately. So in video games, for example, the actor will just be providing the voice as a one-off. The voice can then be cloned and used repeatedly, without further acknowledgment.”

”So where does copyright apply here? And does [a performer] own their whole personality or do they just own their voice? Or their facial expression? Or do I own it because I’m producing this? Or does Rob own it because he’s designed the show?”

”Copyright for us isn’t so much about being paid, it’s about (having the ability to exert) rights over what happens to our work, when it’s disseminated.”

With copyright very much an open question around uses of Gen AI in 2025, the UK government is looking to tackle this uncertainty through legislation, but it’s still unclear whether the new regulations will support creatives’ right to their work or ultimately undermine it. In the meantime, companies like Imminent-XR will be developing their own ethical approaches, hoping they will be able to retrofit into new legislation that emerges.

Next steps: Considerations for copyright, ethics, and creativity

As we move forward, careful consideration must be given to the following key areas:

Technological solutions for protection from unauthorised data scraping: A high priority for the creative industry, Imminent-XR are already exploring novel methods for establishing data provenance, and licensing combining watermarking, crypto meta-data, and online registries, such as those offered by [Adobe’s Content Authenticity Initiative](#).

Ongoing legislative developments around copyright and AI: both the UK and USA are currently considering legislation dealing directly with copyright and licensing with regards to data used for training Gen AI models. The UK consultation intended to inform upcoming regulation concluded in February 2025.

In the meantime for Imminent-XR, they are continuing to develop their ‘proof of concept’ Virtual Theatre Space through integrating ‘chatbot performers’ in VR. They are also evaluating a new system for converting 2D video to ‘glasses-free’ 3D video powered by AI, for home entertainment systems of the future. All the while with one eye on how current geopolitical events, and the rapid developments in AI may help or hinder their progress to market as interactive and immersive content-makers.

Key takeaways

- Digital theatre is a revolutionary way to tell interactive and immersive stories while being accessible to people all over the globe.
- Virtual theatre can bring new forms of immersive performance to audiences to engage audiences and give them agency to participate in the action
- AI is changing the way digital media is created and ethical frameworks are needed to ensure that it is used responsibly, protecting the livelihoods of creatives and performers.

- Due to the current reliance on large LLMs made by external companies it is hard to use a fully known data set when generating assets.
- AI chatbots can help create new immersive exhibitions that the audience can explore without needing a member of the cast to guide them through it, this means that the actor can be in two places at once!

Expert in Residence Spotlight: Mary Stewart-David

Mary Stewart-David is an award-winning Creative Producer, Researcher, and Director of Dillmeadow Media, an independent Musical Theatre Production company and founder of Imminent-XR, a PhD spin-out focused on R&D in XR (Extended Reality) for live performance. She holds an MA in Theatre Directing from Goldsmiths and an MA in Film Production from Westminster, with additional training in Virtual Reality (VR) and Virtual Production (VP). Mary is currently completing a PhD in Interactive Media at the University of York, School of Arts and Creative Technologies.

Expert in Residence Spotlight: Robert Mark Morgan

Rob Morgan is a multi-disciplinary artist, stage designer, speaker, professor, and author of **The Art of Scenic Design: A Practical Guide to the Creative Process**. He has designed everything from theme parks to stained glass, and his experiences as a designer inform his research on creativity. Rob has worked on a wide range of projects, including the **Avatar the Exhibition** museum exhibit, which toured the U.S. and Canada. He currently teaches at Washington University, after three years at the University of Washington in Seattle.

Expert in Residence Spotlight: David Gochfeld

David Gochfeld is an award-winning XR creator, theatrical director, performer, and researcher focused on XR technologies for immersive storytelling. His pioneering work in live performance in virtual reality has been showcased at festivals worldwide, including Tribeca, Raindance, and the Venice Biennale Cinema. David advises theatre companies in the US, UK, and Europe on interactive and immersive technologies for theatrical productions. He is currently the Performance Lab Fellow at the Royal Central School of Speech and Drama in London, investigating storytelling, motion capture, and HCI in shared virtual environments.

Highlights from *The Turing Way Practitioners Hub*

Participating in the Alan Turing Institute's 2024 SME Cohort of 'Experts in Residence' has been a transformative experience for Imminent-XR (a PhD spinout and tech-start-up, specialising in Live Performance in Virtual Production), working alongside our sister company, Dillmeadow Media, (high tech content creators for traditional theatre and music production). Both companies are having to embrace the benefits and drawbacks of Generative AI at speed, and the support and resources provided by the Turing have enabled us to lay the foundations of an ethical framework for the uses of AI in all of our creative practices.

Through the cohort, we gained invaluable insights into the ethical implications of the use of Generative AI for making digital twins of human performers and were able to address issues of establishing

digital provenance for our creative output, and uses of LLMs in the design and construction of our Virtual Music Theatre Productions.

The Alan Turing Institute's emphasis on transparency, open-source principles, and ethical precepts has informed every aspect of our work, from the initial design stages to the final production. Their comprehensive approach to the ethical use of AI will encourage us and other companies in the Creative Sector to ensure that our virtual productions are not only innovative but also responsible and inclusive.

Of particular benefit was our engagement with the Alan Turing Institute's contribution to the UK Government's consultation on text and data mining (TDM) around copyright and uses of Gen AI for performance. We provided insights on digital twinning for performers, digital provenance, and protecting our creative output while exploiting the benefits of generative AI for live performance in VR. We are grateful to have had the opportunity to contribute to shaping policies that will impact the future of AI and Creative Industries.

As artists, we are working with organisations like The Alan Turing Institute, Innovate UK Immersive Tech Network, and the Adobe-led Content Authenticity Initiative, to advocate for ethical standards and legal frameworks to protect our work and livelihoods. We believe AI can be a powerful tool for creativity without compromising creators' rights. Human ingenuity will be key in making this happen, ensuring a future where innovation and ethics go hand in hand.

Overall our inclusion as 'experts in residence' with the Turing, has been hugely beneficial to our team members, all of whom are both academics and practitioners, and who will take forward the skills and competencies we have acquired through working with the Turing, to meet the complex challenges around the ethical uses of AI in our commercial production processes going forward.

Mary Stewart-David

Imminent-XR & Dillmeadow Media

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The Turing Way Practitioner's Hub, designed and launched in 2023 by Dr Sharan, aims to accelerate the adoption of best practices. Through a six-month cohort-based program, the Hub facilitates knowledge sharing, skill exchange, case study co-creation, and the adoption of open science practices. It also fosters a network of 'Experts in Residence' across partnering organisations.

For any comments, questions or collaboration with *The Turing Way*, please email: turing-way@turing.ac.uk.

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